

DIGITAL PAYMENT SYSTEM IN RURAL INDIA AFTER DEMONETIZATION

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ABSTRACT

India is a vast country with 63 percent rural population. Any project of economic development will not be successful if villages are not been part of it. In the era of science and knowledge, the information technology has played crucial role in the process of development and touched every aspect of life. The banking and finance sector are using technology exactingly service delivery. The demonetization drive launched by govt of India on 8 Sep 2016 push the country to use alternative method of payment. The situation arises with Covid-19 aggravated the problem and urge the use of electronic method to financial transactions. Eventually, India's path of cashless economy became compelling and digitalization drive became prime focus of governmental policy. Lack of infrastructure, digital illiteracy, doubt and mistrust, unwillingness etc. have been the conventional hurdle in way of digitalization of payment system in rural area. But a number of exclusive initiatives have made the way easier. The accessibility and utilisation of different digital payment system such as Aadhar pay, Paytm, IMPS, UPI, Bank PoS machines etc. in rural area had increased the number and value of digital payment over time. Many government schemes which are being operated in online mode had added demand for use of digital mode of transaction in rural area. As a result, total retail digital payment which was 5455 lakhs in December 2015 increased with a combined annual growth rate (CAGR) of 56% to 32509 lakhs in December 2019 and value of these transactions increased from Rs 928 thousand crores to Rs 2682 thousand crores, recording a CAGR of 30% during the same period. Consistent increase in use of digital mode in retail payments along with the profound revamping of cash payment system, indicates increasing acceptance digital payments vis-à-vis cash payment methods. Comparing the use and growth of digital payment in rural area with that of urban area impulses the need of special attention to remove bottlenecks in wider acquiescence of the digital payments in rural area. Setting up Payments Infrastructure Development Fund (PIDF) by RBI is example of good step in right direction. Government of India's initiatives like Digital Finance for Rural

India: Creating Awareness and Access through Common Service Centres (CSCs), Bharat Net Programme will be able to transform rural India as active leader of cashless economy.

Key Worlds: *Digital Payment, Cashless Economy, Aadhar Pay, Paytm, Demonetization*

INTRODUCTION:

We are living in the era of technology. The advancement of technology has made the work faster, convenient and cheaper. Thus, obviously the Indian banking sector also have been taken all initiatives of utilizing advanced technologies with a caution of security. The revolution of digitalization of banking services has gone a long way touching every aspect of banking structure. The payment system in Indian banking sector has traveled faster matching with the other developed countries, specifically during the time after demonetization followed by the Covid-19 crisis. Furthermore, the digitalization process maintained its pace in rural areas as well, impacted the nature and quantum of banking services.

It is estimated that almost all payments were to be made by cash in India in 2010 which reduced to 89 percent in 2020 implies that about 11 percent of all retail transactions in India were made in digital mode. Statistics of the RBI indicates the pace of digitalization of payment system in Indian banking sector. The volume of payment transactions between 2012 and 2017 grew fast with a CAGR of 40% showing perceptiveness for non- cash payment modes. The cashless transaction which was 56.4% in 2016 during the demonetization period, grew by 44.8% in 2017 even cash availability had normalized after demonetization. Even faster growth of non-cash payments (54.3%) in the next financial year 2018-19 is evidence of digital payments slowly becoming a habit of the users. The intensified use of non- cash payment method is further extended by the circumstance of Covid-19. When our country stepped in the path of cashless economy, a number of initiatives were being taken for the digitalization of the payment system. Banks being the main player of money market were expected to intensify and expand their digitalization process. Resultantly Indian economy including rural sector witnessed unprecedented utilisation of technology in financial transactions.

India comes second in terms of largest users of telecommunication and digital equipments, as per a report of the World Bank. More than 25 per cent of Indian uses smart mobiles, but only 6 out of 100 mobile users in India knows its proper use, especially for the utility services. Promoting banking services for wider reach the government has stimulated zero balance accounts for poor people especially in rural area. More than 45.89 crores (as on 29 Jun 2022) saving bank accounts had been opened under only one scheme of Jan-Dhan Yojana.

But people are not responding similarly in terms of usages of the accounts. E-infrastructure and information technology have been proved to be essential ingredient of an efficient banking system. Indian banks are very progressively adopting the modern technology and professionally exploring the opportunities. Nonetheless, there are significant risks to security in online banking

or digitized payment system, but online banking services is being appreciated broadly in India. Furthermore, under the 'Digital India' campaign of our Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi, all the rural post offices (12,000 plus) are being planned to be linked with payment banking using IT facilities. Additionally, digitization of banking services in India will also be helpful to control of black money and rampant corruption.

OBJECTIVE AND METHODOLOGY:

The 'Digital India' drive launched by Government of India encompasses full digitalization of the entire banking and payment system. Developing e-infrastructure in banking sector is one part of the movement whereas the utilisation of digital services and transactions is another vital aspect. More importantly, extension of digital campaign in wider rural area has been one of the challenging issues on account of – (i) infrastructural setup in rural India is severely back dated and inadequate and (ii) maximum users in rural areas have little knowledge of operating digital service delivery equipments such as Smartphones, ATM, Cards etc. Even though more than 70 percent people use smart mobile phone in villages, most of rural people rely only on conventional banking instruments such as cash, cheques, withdrawal etc. This article is an effort to review the progress of Digital India campaign in banking sector and try to identify the hurdle in way of digital payment system especially in rural area. This study is based on secondary data availed from different sources and analyzed using statistical tools to infer the concrete solution for speedy digitalization of payment system in rural India.

DIGITAL PAYMENT IN RURAL AREA:

A number of steps have been taken for faster digitalization of banking network and delivery system in rural area. Cash-less transactions have been encouraged by supporting and motivating suppliers and consumers both. In a targeted scheme to appoint banking correspondents (BCs) for providing effective training of cashless transactions around 6 lakhs volunteers have been engaged so far. Additionally, every village shopkeeper will be getting Rs. 100 as an incentive for completing transaction- payment or receipt- using digital platform. More than three million rural people have enrolled themselves under the e-economy module around 1,55,000 merchants have opted to use digital payment platform. When, government of India started demonetization on 8th November, 2016 the strategic changes to promote digital payment became imperative. To cope up the situation of low cash availability in the economy two payment systems - namely UPI and USSD- have been upgraded by the National Payment Corporation of India to make them easy and accessible at wider coverage. Since people in villages are much more comfortable with use of finger-prints therefore incorporation of same would increase number of digital payments. Some studies acknowledged that there are 1.1 million active workers in rural area having bank account under the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGA) but only around 34 per cent them have their Aadhaar-linked with the bank account. In its review meeting conducted Kant panel it was affirmed that out of the total 60,000

ration shops in villages only around 35 per cent had hand machines which can analyze biometrics of MGNREGA workers.

Figure 1: Digital Buying in India (in million)

Source: Statinvestor, downloaded on 14 Jul 2022 from [Number of digital buyers in India \(statinvestor.com\)](https://www.statista.com/statistics/1088117/number-of-digital-buyers-in-india/)

* As estimated by the [Statista](https://www.statista.com/statistics/1088117/number-of-digital-buyers-in-india/) , 2016

As estimated by the [Online shoppers in India 2020 | Statista](https://www.statista.com/statistics/1088117/number-of-digital-buyers-in-india/)

Figure 1 portrays the significant rise of digitized buying in India. Although, figure indicates reduction of users on digital shopping platforms in recent two years, it may be because of easing covid-19 situation and people started physical shop shopping, but more than 30 crores buyers using online mode of shopping which is a sign of transforming India to be digital. However, it has been evaluated that rural youth are much more affirmative to go cashless, which is very motivating for rapid digital process in rural area.

The non-cash payment has emerged as more effectiveness tool after demonetization, specifically in cities and metros. Table 1 depicts the progress of digital payment practice in India after demonetization along with the increased use of debit and credit cards. There is significant increase in volume and value of digital transaction vis-à-vis paper-based transaction. The number of card payment transaction which were 47486 lakhs in 2017-18 increased to 73012 in 2019-20.

The value of card based transactions also increased by more than 67 percent from Rs 919035 to Rs 1535765 during the period of two years from 2017-18 to 2019-20.

Table 1. Payment System Indicators – Annual Turnover (April-March)

Items	Volume (Lakh)			Value (₹ Crore)		
	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
Settlement Systems	35	36	36	10,74,80,202	11,65,51,038	13,41,50,192
Large Value – RTGS	1,244	1,366	1,507	11,67,12,478	13,56,88,187	13,11,56,475
Retail Credit Transfers	58,793	1,18,750	2,06,661	1,88,14,287	2,60,97,655	2,85,72,100
Aadhaar Pay	20	68	91	78	815	1,303
ECS Dr	15	9	1	972	1,260	39
NACH Dr	3,738	6,299	8,768	3,98,211	6,54,138	8,24,491
NETC	15	6	97	39	20	203
Credit Cards	14,052	17,626	21,773	4,58,965	6,03,413	7,30,895
Debit Cards	33,434	44,143	51,239	4,60,070	5,93,475	8,04,870
Prepaid	34,591	46,072	53,318	1,41,634	2,13,323	2,15,558

Source: Department of Payment and Settlement Systems (DPSS), Reserve Bank of India, August 25, 2020

To have more specific data of electronic payments instruments been used in India surfaces the growth story of improved use of digital methods. In 2017-18, around 20 lakhs transaction took place using BHIM Aadhar Pay which increased to more than 91 lakhs in 2019-20 whereas the amount of transaction increased from Rs 78 crores to Rs 1303 crores during same period of two years. The NETC (Linked to Bank Account) payment system also shown the growth from 15 lakhs transaction to 97 lakhs in two years' time from 2017-18 to 2019-20 and value of these transaction increased from Rs 39 crores to Rs 203 crores in the same two years. The prepaid digital payments also increased from 34591 lakhs to 53318 lakhs amounting from Rs 141634 crores to Rs 215558 crores during two years after the demonetization took place.

Figure 2 highlights the progress of total digital payment over the paper-based traditional methods. Paper based transaction which were 11,713 lakhs in 2017-18 reduced to 11,238 lakhs in 2018-19 and 10,414 lakhs in 2019-2020. Apparently, the value of paper based conventional transaction has also been reduced from Rs 82,46,065 crores in 2018-19 to Rs 78,24,821 crores in 2019-2020. Whereas the number of digital transactions increased from 1,45,902 lakhs in 2017-18 and to 2,34,339 lakhs in 2018-19 and to 3,43,455 lakhs in 2019-2020. The value of digitalized transaction payments has also been increased from Rs 13,69,86,734 crores in 2017-18 to Rs 16,23,05,934 crores in 2019-2020.

Figure 2: Payment System in India

Source: Department of Payment and Settlement Systems (DPSS), Reserve Bank of India, August 25, 2020.

Notwithstanding with the above data which shows the status of payment system in the country, there is dire requirement of maintaining the effectiveness of digital transactions. In fact, rural economy is lagging behind in term of accessibility and uses of banking services especially in digital mode so transferring rural economy into cashless economy need special attention.

Figure 3: Declining Digital Transaction in Rural India

Source: Waghmare, A. (2017), National Payments Corporation of India, RBI.

There are studies showing decline of online transaction in rural area post demonetization. Waghmare (2017) highlighted that after demonetization rural India witnessed significant decline in the digital transaction and amount of the transaction in next three months. This might be due to the lower knowledge of handling cashless transaction with the existing rural banking infrastructure. Lack of digital awareness and distrust on its effectiveness might have contributed in the decline of online transaction. Recapitalization after was the other reason for reduced transaction which led people to have more cash added with fear of being notice for assumably unwarranted cash transaction (Figure 3). Hence, although digital banking became inevitable in the backdrop of demonetization, lack of knowledge, poor infrastructure and less faith in unusual

system led to such a decline of digital transaction in succeeding months digitalization from Rs 935,500,000 in December 2016 to Rs 763,000,000 in February 2017.

Nevertheless, these data are related to very short period, possibly affected by temporary factors, but it cautions the importance of rural sector in success of digital banking movement. Rural sector retains significant position for the economic development of India. The commencement of demonetization was a metamorphosing event in modern era that led to revamping market structure of Indian economy. As situation aggravated with the Covid-19 pandemic, significant growth in the number of users of digital payment interface had been projected. Increasing penetration of mobile internet in rural interior, addition of new digital interface like UPI and inception of e-wallets/ payment apps will add the pace in non-cash transactions. Convenience and confidence on digital payments with added incentives will help transforming India into digital economy.

DIGITAL PAYMENT - 'AADHAAR PAY':

Government has been striving hard to promote digital payment among the ignorant and poor people of rural area. The existing mode of digital transactions, such as cards and online payments, require PIN and password which seems to be difficult and risky for a humble customer. Aadhaar Pay is a fingerprints-based interface enables users to make financial transactions using Aadhar database. It is assumably more secure system as a merchant has to have validated Aadhaar number and fingerprint of the customer with name of the bank for formulating a delivery system in this mode. UIDAI acclaimed advantages of this method as – (i) it can be attached with any android-based phone, (ii) it just requires a finger biometric device attached to the phone, (iii) customer does not require to have a phone and (iv) outmost secure as the digital transactions are validated on real time basis. The Government of India initially authored five selected public sector banks namely, Syndicate Bank, Andhra Bank, State Bank of India, IDFC Bank and IndusInd bank to enroll at least 30–40 merchants per branch to formulate Aadhaar Pay based cashless payments module. Later more banks included in this pilot project to extend Aadhaar Pay system among merchants in rural India. Recently, around 14 commercial banks are part of Aadhaar Pay system which assists to enhance the economic infrastructure for non-cash transaction, especially in rural hinterland.

Furthermore, it is necessary to be comparatively cost effective for any mode to become universally acceptable and so continuous efforts are made to reduce the cost of the biometric device. Government has also introduced incentive-based model to encourage the merchants for more use to reduce cost. Although the Aadhaar Pay transactions are comparatively more secure on account of full proof processes and comprehensive instruments but, as happened with all digital method, the security breaches have also been issues of serious concerns. The rectification system is made more effective in the Aadhaar Pay application. In case of any misuses or exploitation, the merchant would be traceable as the location and details are properly recorded. Definitely, expansion of digital transaction system in rural area of the country, such as 'Aadhaar

Pay' system, has certain constraints. Aadhar Pay is highly dependent on internet coverage as required data for fund transfer. This is fact that the internet coverage and speed in rural areas is still a long-awaited requirement. By November 2019 the total broadband subscribers were 65.9 crores out of which 64 crores were wireless broadband. Eventually, unreliable internet connectivity and poor speed/services can shrink the entire e-payment system so, this hurdle needs to be shortened.

DIGITAL PAYMENT-PAYTM:

Paytm is India's largest and the most used digital payments company. Paytm has launched a specially devised service kit suitable for specific need of rural India. Generally Paytm provides different interface to be use for payments and receipts but it is improvised to offer additional facility for merchants to execute their deals. Keeping requirement of the Agro-merchant in view Paytm also devised specific Paytm platform to facilitate payment structure of the partner company. Paytm postpaid is a kind of credit facility offered by the platform to extend the acceptability and uses of the App. It also has some exclusive schemes for farmers in which they can avail loans for agricultural needs. These loans can be taken as part of Mudra Loan Scheme of the government of India where no need of significant security is there. The entire process is completed digitally and amount is also disbursed in digital form. The eligibility is determined on the basis of total transaction value completed on Paytm platform.

Thus, this tool is very supportive for faster digitalization of transaction in villages. It also facilitates to modify the payment options according to the paying capability and convenience of the borrower. Most recently new innovative feature is added in payment method in which internet is not compulsory. In this a customer has registered his mobile number with his Paytm account. In case he has to transfer amount to anyone he has to dial on a toll-free number of Paytm and enter the amount and phone number of the recipient. The amount will be transferred immediately. So, this method is also useful in the most rural areas of the country where internet facility is not adequate. National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI) has adopted this concept in the Aadhaar Pay app system also.

CUSTOMERS' PERSPECTIVE TOWARDS DIGITAL PAYMENT SYSTEM:

Refer Ratan Watal, former Finance Secretary, Indian payment system constituted by 55.8 percent of the total transaction taking place in the economy which was noticeably increased by 25 percent in one year during demonetization. Reserve Bank of India had also assessed the significant increase in the digital payments adoption rate on account of demonetization which slowed down in early a few months of 2017. The data given in table 2 reflect different parameters of undisputed growth in the acceptance of digital payments in next two years.

Table 2: Progress of Digitalization from Cash to Electronic

Parameter	Year	
	205-16	2018-19
Debit Cards (in lakhs)	6615	9058
Credit Cards (in lakhs)	245	471
ATM (in thousands)	212	222
PoS (in lakhs)	13.86	37.22
Currency in circulation (as GDP percentage)	12.1	11.2
Digital transaction (as GDP percentage)	668	862
Branches of SCBs (total)	1,26,643	1,45,426
Branches of SCBs (rural)	48,140	51,507

Source: Reserve Bank of India, Department of Payment and Settlement Systems, Mumbai.

According to the report of credit card database, the increased number of credit and debit cards complying with increased number of Point of Sale (PoS) have been catalyst in process of digitalization of payment system. The move is also supported with amplified number of branches of scheduled commercial banks which increased by 3.5% in five years after 2015.

Apparently, people have better accessibility of banking services and so getting habit of paying in form of digital transaction using a debit or credit card. Resultantly, the value of cash withdraw as percentage of GDP has decreased from 18.44% in 2015-16 to 17.44% in 2018-19. Not only the total number of debit and credit cards increased in recent years but also card-related transactions have increased with a significantly high rate. Decrease in currency in circulation as percentage of GDP from 12.1% in 2015-16 to 11.2% in 2018-19 along with increase in digital payments amount as percentage to GDP from 668% in 2015-16 and 730% in 2016-17 and to 862% in 2018-19 is evidence of increased relative importance of digital payment system in post demonetization period.

The technological innovation and its adaptation in payment system opened different gateway for more convenient and confident methods of digital transactions. The acceptance of digital method by people of country especially in rural areas can be attributed to many factors such as easy to use, honest transparency and adoptive accessibility.

Adding to the hitches in adaptation of digital payment the major drawbacks include diseconomies of scale, complications in use, high price of equipments and risk factors. Consumer perspective for digital payments especially using mobile technologies has been studied which found that mobile payment adoption directly related with lack of other payment methods but also affected by a few situational factors.

Figure 4. Impacting Factors of Digital Payments

Source: Shakir, Wasim, and Safiuddin (2017).

In Indian context, there have been many factors influencing the adaptation of digital mode of payment. Figure 4 significantly demonstrate the factors effective for acceptance and growth of digital payments among customers. However, there are also many other significant aspects which warrant the requirement of more user friendly and secure payment options in digital mode. The transition from cash to cashless economy has been triggered by the demonetization but was very much accelerated during the Covid-19 situation.

Altogether, the shift toward digital economy have provided many options to merchants, customers, government, functionaries and bankers extensively as it abetted to escalated transparency. It has provided a convenient methodology to expand and accelerate the formal economy. Based on a survey of 205 merchant who were using digital mode, Shakir, Wasim, and Safiuddin (2017) established that customer's demand for digital payment is the most influential factor for digital transaction. The other factors include safety, saving energy and time, convenience of use and maintaining of records and helpful in expanding business.

CHALLENGES IN EXPANSION OF DIGITAL PAYMENT SYSTEM IN RURAL AREA:

The government and nationalized banks have been trying hard for faster digitalization of payment system in India. Actually, it is a big challenge to provide cheap banking and financial services through digital mode which is easily accessible to the vast population of rural India. India is the country of rural dominance where more than 800 million people (about 65% of total population) living in its more than 6.4 lakh villages but only 20.26% of rural people have internet accessibility. Although in cities of India every two out of three person have internet facility.

Rural India lacks in basic infrastructures which are directly and indirectly related to the expansion of electronic mode of financial transactions.

When demonetization urged our country to go less-cash or more digitalized for payments and service delivery, the expansion of required infrastructures and removal of other bottlenecks become inevitable. The barriers in transformation of economy into cashless especially in rural area engrossed the policy maker when the situation of low cash in the economy intensified by the Covid-19 pandemic. Hence a multi-faced and inclusive programme is needed to overcome specific challenges of rural India.

Financial illiteracy is the most important but least thought about concept in rural areas. It is not merely the matter of fund but also getting ease in complex financial procedures. Financial literacy is not the problem visualized by rural people as does not stand in competition of other necessities. Rural people better try to avoid the financial complexities at the place of trying to make use of it. The rural population, although getting in habit of using digital accessories, but are very less aware of digital knowledge and equipments like computer and smartphone. Most of the grownups are even lack the basic knowledge of digital medium and remains avoided of its complexity. Poor internet connection with an assumably unjustified cost is also keeping the user away from the benefits. The frequent event of cheating and misbehave in financial sector tarnished the trust of noble rural people.

They have been subjected to denial of payment on account of various reason including lack of fund, ill-function of the computer system, network and technical issues. It makes them even more distrustful in case of digital transaction especially without human interface on account of none's responsibility in case of possible fraud. There are very limited number of person and business entities which make/accept digital transaction in rural areas. Hence people force to go for a non-digital mode of payment and thus digital movement not getting pace in rural area. The worry is further added by limit on number of transactions which itself contracts the use of digital mode of payment.

Merchants in rural areas are very reluctant in setting up business using PoS. Despite of incentives and discounts are offered by almost every provider but the adoption rate of point-of-sale mechanism in rural area is very low. This may be because of people want to hide many things as a matter of human nature. Rural area is still lacking of adequate smartphone, network coverage, speedy internet connectivity, uninterrupted electricity, consumer friendly banking services. Government of India promoted financial inclusion of rural people through opening account under the Jan Dhan Yojana but most of these accounts are dormant and randomly used for governmental schemes only.

Banking habit in poor and ignorant group of people remains low and so becomes difficult in transition from cash to cashless. Most of the needs of rural people are fulfilled locally and cash transactions is most liked method. The informal or unorganized nature of rural economy

supported suitability by cash transaction and hence digitalization of rural economy is difficult task. Poverty is the mother of every evil and biggest hurdle in path of any change. Internet facility and smart mobile phones are still luxuries for most to rural poor people. Heavily technology dependent digital payment system is out of reach for many in rural area hence, faster transformation of economy into digitalized will only be possible on the base of an economically viable system.

KEY SOLUTIONS:

Adequate and appropriate infrastructure is basic need for any transformation. Wider coverage of digital mode of transaction in rural area greatly need affordable smartphone with user friendly interface in regional languages. Government of India's high aimed 'Bharat Net Project' which expected to cover all 6.4 lakhs villages expected to provide smooth and speedy internet with uninterrupted electricity supply. The Telephone Regulation Authority of India (TRAI) is also tasked to devise village friendly schemes for better and cheap internet connectivity. Joining hands by services provider can increase the internet delivery points like hotspots, mobile internet and hence affordable online services will improve the basis infrastructure in rural area for faster financial digitalization. Improvement in literacy especially digital literacy is most important aspect in adoption of digital mode of payments for cashless economy. Under 'Digital India' mission government of India as provisioned to set up Common Service Center (CSC) for providing digital assistance to the rural humble people. Need is to propagate computer related knowledge by all mode including compulsory computer education in schools. Additionally, the village representatives and the self-help groups (SHGs) should be trained and stimulated to propagate digital literacy in local vicinity.

Though trust building is a time taking process but appropriate advertisement strategies and different promotional drive can help in bringing people in the loop. Government should introduce many incentive schemes, such as 'Lucky Grahak Yojana' for customer and 'Digi-Dhan Vyapar Yojana' for business persons for motivation for adopting non-cash mode of transaction. Other service provide must join hands in this drive. More initiatives need to be taken to formalize the rural economy. Digitization of land records and every transaction over two lakh rupees to be done electronically are a few examples of getting rural economy into records. More banking services and banking habits, implementation of government schemes in electronic mode, accounting of every activity etc. will bring rural economy in right path and make the digitalization process faster. Thus, digitalization and regularization are interdependent and mutual supporting process and greatly needed in case of rural economy.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

The process of digitalization of payment system in India was started long back in beginning of 21st century but it was extremely induced by the demonetization and accelerated by the Covid-

19 pandemic. Transformation of cash-based economy into cashless economy naturally imbedded on digital transaction as the universally accepted mode, even in the rural part of the country. The Prime Minister's Digital India programme which was launched on July 1, 2015 has indicative of important of digitalization of every activity in the country has become need of time. Setting up CSCs as pivot of Digital Financial services under the IT Ministry scheme assumed to provide support to the digital drive, specifically in rural India. The government of India has also set up fund with initially ₹ 65.625 crores to promote use of different digital financial services especially till uncovered sectors. To accelerate financial inclusion in rural area of the seven states of north-eastern region, the RBI has also created a fund with ₹ 345 crores. Bharat Net Project is another flagship programme to develop digital infrastructure across the country. In additional to much more being done by the government; a number of private players are invited to take part in facilitating rural area with adequate modern infrastructure. Reduction in cost on account of economies of scale and advancement of technology must be shared by the rural area.

A report by McKinsey report says that despite of intemperate urbanization in coming year rural population will remain two third of the total marketable economy of India by 2025. Apparently, digitalization of Indian economy will remain incomplete without proper digitalization of rural area. Conventionally, rural area has been lab of hurdles in way of implementing new programmes. Lesser outcome of any scheme of rural development can be attributed to its typical nature and usual bottlenecks. The digitalization of financial services has not taken place with the expected speed owing to slow growth in rural area. Hence there is a need to devise special programmes for specific digitalization of rural area keeping its weakness and strength in mind. For example, one of the unique features may be added in digital payments system to enable it useful in the areas where banks and internet is not available. The expansion of digital platforms up to the remote area of the country is key indicator and accelerator of economic growth, and so additional steps needs to be taken to speed up digital drive in rural area by removing the bottlenecks. With mobile and internet reaching all corners rural India is rapidly embracing the digital mode of payments, making path of transforming India into a cashless economy.

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